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“THE WOMAN BEHIND THE SMILE”

I have admired her for so long,
her quiet grace, her voice so strong;
the way she speaks, the words she gives,
the way her gentle wisdom lives.

Once, I dreamed to be the same,
to walk like her, to earn her name;
yet I have learned what I can see,
one of a kind is what she will be.

Her heart is full of tender light,
though hidden well from common sight;
her kindness rests behind her smile,
and in her voice, it blooms a while.

There was a time I judged her wrong,
perhaps because I was not strong;
I was young and quick to feel,
not yet wise enough to heal.

But now I know, in her own way,
her love still reached me day by day;
she hid it under strength and pride,
a softer heart kept safe inside.

Yes, she is strong, and I admire
the courage shaped by grief and fire;
the trials that tried to break her through
made her wiser, brave, and true.

I wrote these lines for her to see
how much her life has meant to me;

and though my voice may fail to start,
I hope this poem can speak my heart.

